

Effect of 2,4-D and kinetin on callus induction and plant regeneration with IR50 seeds in MS medium.

Callus induction medium				Regeneration medium ^a			
2,4-D (mg/liter)	Kinetin (mg/liter)	Seeds inoculated (no.)	Seeds producing calli (no.)	Callus production (%)	Calli transferred (no.)	Calli regenerated (no.)	Regeneration (%)
0.0	0.0	74	—	—	—	—	—
0.5	0.0	68	10	14.7	36	3	8.3
0.5	0.5	74	12	16.2	38	4	10.5
0.5	1.0	72	12	16.6	42	6	14.3
1.0	0.0	74	31	41.8	44	8	18.2
1.0	0.5	73	34	46.6	44	11	25.0
1.0	1.0	72	36	50.0	42	7	16.6
1.5	0.0	68	37	54.4	40	9	22.5
1.5	0.5	74	42	56.7	38	8	21.4
1.5	1.0	69	42	60.8	42	6	14.3
2.0	0.0	72	46	63.8	32	2	6.2
2.0	0.5	68	42	61.7	44	18	40.9 ^b
2.0	1.0	67	29	43.2	42	+	—
5.0	0.0	72	26	36.1	32	+	—
5.0	0.5	74	28	37.8	32	+	—
5.0	1.0	74	25	33.7	36	+	—

^a Regeneration medium = basal medium + 1 mg kinetin/liter + 1 mg NAA/liter. + = rhizogenesis.

^b Formation of somatic embryos.

Callus pieces were transferred to regeneration medium containing kinetin and NAA at a concentration of 1 mg/ liter each. Regeneration was better from calli induced from the C medium containing 2 mg 2,4-D/liter and 0.5 mg kinetin/ liter through the process of somatic embryogenesis (established by histological studies).

The somatic embryos formed had two distinct poles and were attached to the callus piece through their broader surface. Embryoids of different shapes were also traced out during early stages of embryogenesis. Other treatments did not yield somatic embryos. □

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A medium-duration, high-yielding, scented hybrid rice

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We have identified tall, late-maturing, scented cultivar Basmati 370 as a

complete restorer for the CMS line IR46830A.

Hybrid IR46830A/ Basmati 370 was evaluated for yield and quality components (Table 1,2). The hybrid flowered earlier and was shorter than the better parent. Positive and significant heterosis over the better parent was recorded for most characters. Increase in grain yield/ plant was due

primarily to more effective tillers/ plant and higher 1,000-grain weight. Although yield of the hybrid was not significantly higher than that of check variety Pant Dhan 4, better quality attributes make it more suitable for commercial production. Its medium growth duration would make it suitable for a rice - wheat cropping pattern. □

Table 1. Mean performance of the hybrid IR46830A/Basmati 370, and estimates of heterosis over the better parent and check variety Pant Dhan 4. ^a Pantnagar, India, 1988.

Character	Mean for F ₁	Heterosis ^b	
		Better parent	Check
Days to 50% flowering	95.0	-24.60*	-20.16*
Plant height (cm)	137.2	-12.50*	-30.66*
Effective tillers/ plant (no.)	20.8	44.45*	23.80*
Length of panicle (cm)	32.2	5.59	20.81*
Primary branches/ panicle (no.)	12.2	19.60*	-9.83
Secondary branches/ panicle (no.)	40.4	36.50*	34.50*
Spikelets/panicle (no.)	202.6	35.25*	30.20*
Grains/panicle (no.)	164.0	19.80*	17.64*
1000-grain weight (g)	22.9	31.24*	-0.62
Grain yield/plant (g)	63.0	83.89*	16.50

^a Av of 5 plants. ^b* = significant at 5% level.

Table 2. Mean value for 5 grain quality traits in Basmati 370, hybrid IR46830A/Basmati 370, and Pant Dhan 4. ^a Pantnagar, India, 1988.

Character studied	Basmati 370	Hybrid	Pant Dhan 4
Length of grain (mm)	7.88	7.38	6.34
Breadth of grain (mm)	1.72	2.04	2.10
L/B ratio	4.58	3.61	3.11
Alkali digestion value	2.25	3.00	3.50
Aroma	Strong	Intermediate	—

^a Av of 5 replications.

Evaluation of some F₁ rice hybrids developed using MR365A as CMS line

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We evaluated yield and heterosis of eight F₁ rice hybrids developed using MR365A (CMS line developed at IRRRI

Jan-May 1984. The hybrids, Cisadane, and IR36 were transplanted at 20- × 20-cm spacing in 2- × 5-m plots, with 2 replications. Fertilizer was 135-45-45 kg NPK/ha.

Hybrid combinations MR365A/ IR36, MR365A/IR52, and MR365A/BR10 yielded about 1 t/ha more than Cisadane and showed significant heterosis (14.63-27.65%) (see table). For